

AN ADVANCED SENSOR FOR AUTOMATED DOCKING

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Abstract

This paper describes the current developments in video-based sensors at the Marshall Space Flight Center. The Advanced Video Guidance Sensor is the latest in a line of video-based sensors designed for use in automated docking systems. The X-33, X-34, X-38, and X-40 are all spacecraft designed to be unpiloted vehicles; such vehicles will require a sensor system that will provide adequate data for the vehicle to accomplish its mission. One of the primary tasks planned for re-usable launch vehicles is to resupply the space station. In order to approach the space station in a self-guided manner, the vehicle must have a reliable and accurate sensor system to provide relative position and attitude information between the vehicle and the space station. The Advanced Video Guidance Sensor is being designed and built to meet this requirement, particularly for the Demonstration of Autonomous Rendezvous Technology (DART), as well as requirements for other vehicles docking to a variety of target spacecraft.

Introduction

Spacecraft are facing an increasing need for methods of performing Automated Rendezvous and Docking (AR&D) and Automated Rendezvous and Capture (AR&C). Some of the spacecraft that will require such an AR&D system include the automated vehicles that will refuel and resupply the Space Station, spacecraft that will participate in the Mars Sample Return mission, and spacecraft that will perform automated resupply and maintenance of satellites. One of the key elements of any AR&D system is the sensor used for the final approach and docking/berthing. The sensor must be reliable, able to operate in shadow or full sunlight, and provide data at a rate sufficient for the Guidance, Navigation, and Control (GN&C) system to control the chase vehicle properly. Such a sensor

has been under development for the last decade at the Marshall Space Flight Center (MSFC).

Advanced Video Guidance Sensor

The Advanced Video Guidance Sensor (AVGS) is a video-based sensor that is being developed for use in the proximity operations stage of AR&D. It is being designed to acquire and track a target at ranges up to 500 meters using a CMOS-based video sensor. The sensor will operate at ranges down to 0.5 meters. It outputs the relative positions and attitudes between the sensor and the target.

Automated Rendezvous and Docking

There are several components that make up an AR&D system. Other than the spacecraft itself, the components include an on-board computer (OBC), control software that calculates the correct thruster firings to achieve the vehicle's goal, a sensor system used for long-range (rendezvous) operations, a sensor used for short range (proximity) operations, and a grapple mechanism or fixture to allow the system to be attached to its target vehicle.

On-Board Computer

The OBC is the brains of the spacecraft. It interfaces with all of the sensors and control systems on the spacecraft, making the sensor data available to all of the programs that require that information. The OBC also keeps the back-up control system updated in case the spacecraft needs to perform a Collision Avoidance Maneuver (CAM). The OBC handles the data manipulation and transfer for ground monitoring purposes.

AR&D Software

The software handles all of the standard spacecraft functions (command and data handling, thruster firing, etc.) as well as the functions peculiar to an AR&D system. Such special functions

include the automated computation and control for the orbital phasing of the chase vehicle and the target vehicle, the rendezvous portion of the automated docking, and the control algorithms for the proximity operations and final dock/berth. If there were active docking mechanisms on board, the software would control their operation. The software/OBC is also responsible for all of the system monitoring, status, and diagnostics. Such self-knowledge is critical in an automated system with the capability of causing great damage if it did not perform properly.

Long Range (Rendezvous) Sensor

An AR&D system requires some type of sensor that provides enough information about the

target and chase vehicle locations to allow the two spacecraft to end up in the same orbit within a reasonable proximity of each other (around a kilometer). In the ground-test AR&D system developed at MSFC, the Global Positioning System (GPS) was used as the rendezvous sensor. Since the target's orbital position is known before flight, GPS could provide the information necessary for the chase vehicle to know its own orbit well enough to get within a kilometer of the target vehicle. If the target spacecraft had a suitable GPS receiver onboard and could transmit enough of its own GPS information to the chase vehicle, the two spacecraft could approach each other very closely and with an error bound of less than 10 meters.

Figure 1: Advanced Video Guidance Sensor Block Diagram

Short Range Sensor

For the final docking/berthing of the two vehicles, the AR&D system needs a sensor that provides relative positions and attitudes between the chase vehicle and the target vehicle. The Video Guidance Sensor (VGS) was developed a few years ago for that purpose, and an improved version of the VGS (the subject of this paper) is currently under development. This sensor must be able to handle the transition from rendezvous to proximity operations and be able to pick up where the rendezvous sensor leaves off.

Docking Mechanism

The final component needed for an AR&D system is a mechanism for its final contact with the target vehicle. This may be an active mechanism on the chase vehicle, a mechanism designed to latch the two spacecraft together, or it may be a passive mechanism such as a set of bars or handles that the target spacecraft latches on to.

All of these components are important to the success of an AR&D system, but with the exception of the close-range sensor, all of the components are

at a high readiness for use in a spacecraft, thus the MSFC focus on the development of a proximity sensor for AR&D.

AVGS Theory of Operation

The AVGS operates on a fairly simple theory – the tracking of spots on a known target. By tracking only spots, a large amount of image processing/scene understanding is avoided, and since the spots occupy known positions on the target, the sensor can easily determine relative position and attitude data based on the centroids of the spots.

The AVGS consists of two parts: the sensor and the target. The sensor is the active portion of the AVGS. It contains the laser illuminators, the imager, the frame grabber, the image processor, the communications electronics, and all of the support electronics required to have the previous parts work together. See Figure 1. The target is an arrangement of corner-cube retro-reflectors with optical filters in front.

Sensor

The sensor uses two different wavelengths of laser diodes to illuminate the target. One of the wavelengths (the foreground wavelength – currently 940 nm) passes through the filter in front of the retro-reflectors on the target, and the other wavelength (the background wavelength – currently 808 nm) is absorbed by the filters. The system functions by taking a picture of the target illuminated by the foreground lasers. Then the AVGS takes a picture of the target illuminated by the background lasers. The second picture is digitally subtracted from the first, resulting in a very low-noise image with some bright spots at the target reflector locations. After the image subtraction, the DSP processes the resulting intensity data, assembling the pixels that are above the threshold into blobs. The blobs are then screened for size, their centroids are computed, and the relationships between the blobs' positions are used to see if there is a match between the blob pattern and the known target spot pattern. Once the target spots are picked out of all of the blobs, tracking windows are established around the target spots, and the relative positions and attitudes

between the sensor and the target are computed [1]. The image processing sequence is shown in Figure 2 below.

Foreground Image

Background Image

Subtracted Image

Thresholded Image

Image with Tracking window

Figure 2: Image Processing Sequence

When the target is close enough to the sensor, tracking windows are established around each of the target spots. The acquisition cycle requires processing the entire image to find the target. Once the target has been acquired, only the area around the target spots must be processed each cycle, so the processing time is decreased.

Target

The target for the AVGS consists of an array of filtered corner-cube retro-reflectors in a known pattern.

Figure 3: VGS Flight Experiment Target

This target was designed to be used by the VGS for tracking at ranges from 1 meter out to 110 meters. The retro-reflectors are arranged in a pattern of 3-in-a-row with a fourth retro-reflector above the center one at the same distance as the outer two. This target uses clusters of retro-reflectors for each of the long-range target spots and single retro-reflectors for each of the short-range target spots. In each case, the center retro-reflector is raised above the outer ones. This pattern provides good sensitivity to small changes in pitch and yaw. The target recognition software can recognize this pattern easily and can distinguish right side up from upside down at long ranges. This target provides full 6-degree-of-freedom (6-DOF) information at every range when the sensor is tracking the target. It turns out that the GN&C algorithms used for proximity operations don't actually incorporate all 6-DOF information until very close ranges (10 meters in the proto-type systems developed at MSFC.) This means that the

long range target really only needs to provide range and bearing, and a short range target needs to provide the full 6-DOF capability. There are two short-range targets on the VGS target in order to provide the capability for redundancy in a spacecraft – the chase vehicle could have two separate VGSs, with each one centered on one of the two short-range targets.

The planned AVGS target configuration takes into account the need for redundancy as well as the need for extended range. The AVGS target will consist of sets of short-range targets in a pattern on the target spacecraft. Each of the short-range targets could serve as the final target for a different AVGS (to allow for redundancy.) Such a target might be laid out as below.

Figure 4: Possible AVGS Target Configuration

This is a potential layout for a target for the AVGS. The AVGS would use the groups of retro-reflectors in the short-range targets as the long-range target reflectors. The bearing to the target would be based on the position of the targets in the field-of-view (FOV), and the range to the target would be based on the separation between the outer sets of targets. The range would not be completely accurate (since any target yaw would be interpreted as a small change in range), but the measured range would not be in error by more than 7% (at the maximum relative yaw angle of about 20 degrees).

Video Guidance Sensor History

The AVGS is the latest in a line of video-based sensors developed at MSFC for use in automated docking systems. The first system was created in 1988 and was based on a flight sensor that tracked retro-reflectors. It was used to allow a 3-DOF spacecraft simulator to dock with a non-moving target. This system used active illumination of retro-reflectors with passive background subtraction. That only worked well when the background was mostly non-reflective. The next sensor was personal computer (PC) based and used a frame-grabber inside a PC to capture the image data. This system used two wavelengths of laser diodes and filtered retro-reflective target spots. It tracked at 2 Hz out to a range of about 10 meters and was operational in 1989. In 1991, the first DSP-based VGS was built. The DSP was mounted on a card that included a frame grabber, and the card was housed in a PC. This system operated at 5 Hz and utilized two different targets to allow the sensor to work out to about 20 meters. Some of the more important requirements for the VGS included operating at ranges up to 110 meters at a 5 Hz rate [2]. This was the basic design that led to the flight experiment version of the VGS.

In 1993, the Automated Rendezvous and Capture project was started, and a flight experiment planned for the VGS. The flight experiment was designed to test the full capabilities of the VGS.

The VGS was exercised from the minimum range possible on the Shuttle (2.5 meters) out to well beyond the designed maximum range. The flight-experiment VGS met the tracking rate requirement and greatly exceeded the range requirement, tracking at ranges up to 180 meters on orbit [3]. The plan for the flight experiment was laid out in the Flight Experiment Requirements Document [4]. Much was learned from the two flight experiments in 1997 and 1998 [3,5,6], and the results of those experiments led to the preliminary design of the AVGS in 2000.

Current Development

The AVGS is currently under development for use in a flight experiment on the DART. The baseline configuration for the AVGS is a video-sensor based on a high-speed CMOS digital camera.

The baseline configuration will have the scars in place to allow the addition of a laser range finder (for added range capability) and a small camera (for monitoring purposes).

Hardware

The AVGS will incorporate a 1024 x 1024 pixel black and white CMOS imager. The imager outputs data in digital format at up to 250 frames per second. Some of the other components to be described in detail include the laser diodes, FPGAs, DSP, SBC, memory, communications and I/O hardware.

Figure 5 shows the current layout of the camera and image/data processing electronics.

Figure 5: AVGS Digital Electronics

The imager is in the set of smaller cards at the top of Figure 5. The data from the imager (a set of pixels within a rectangular window) is sent by low voltage differential signal (LVDS) to the video capture card. The video capture card contains two megabytes of RAM for use in holding video images and processed video data. The video capture card also has a large PLD that talks to the DSP – the PLD sends the image data to the DSP, and the DSP sends exposure and windowing information to the PLD.

The imager will be mounted on a structure that faces a 45 degree angled turning-mirror (as seen in Figures 1 and 6.) The mirror (shown in Figure 6, along with the imager and lens) is machined to allow the laser diodes to emit up through the glass, allowing the lasers to fire along the bore site of the camera. This method maximizes the amount of light returned from the target retro-reflectors into

the camera lens and thus onto the imager. The two laser wavelengths to be used for the AVGS (808 nm and 940 nm) are fairly close together so that differences in target reflectivity will be minimal between the two wavelengths (ensuring that objects that appear in both the foreground and the background will be subtracted out.) The lasers at each wavelength will be capable of a pulsed output power of approximately 10 W (or 3 W continuous).

Figure 6: AVGS Prototype Camera with Turning Mirror

The DSP that will be used in the AVGS is the Texas Instruments TMS320-VC33. This floating-point processor includes 132KB of on-board RAM, allowing the entire program to run on the DSP itself. This feature allows the software to run much faster than it would if it resided in external memory. The DSP also allows certain instructions to run in parallel with other instructions, allowing further increases in program speed.

The single board computer (SBC) will be responsible for the communications from AVGS to the outside world via RS422 (or possibly RS485). The SBC will pass commands to the DSP and pass data from the DSP to the serial connection. The AVGS will operate in one of three modes: stand-by, acquisition, and tracking; during power-up and reset, the AVGS will perform self-testing before automatically transitioning into stand-by mode. The system will be awaiting commands while in stand-by mode. During acquisition, the AVGS will be hunting for target(s) and putting out status data and spot data for anything that it finds in the FOV. Once the target has been acquired, the AVGS will

automatically transition into tracking mode and will output the relative positions and attitudes at a 20 Hz rate.

Software

The AVGS software will be broken into two components – the DSP software that handles all of the image processing and relative positions and attitude calculations and the SBC software that handles the housekeeping and communications. In addition to this, there will be firmware in the video capture board that takes care of some of the preliminary image processing – scanning the image and performing the image and threshold subtraction.

The DSP software will take in the set of pixels that, after having the background subtracted out, are still above the set threshold. All of the spots in the image will be processed to find the target, and then the spot data will be used to compute the relative positions and attitudes. After the target has been found, only spots within the tracking windows (around the target spots) will be processed.

Specifications

The AVGS has a wide variety of performance requirements including minimum range, maximum range, FOV, accuracy, data output, lighting constraints, etc. Also, since the AVGS is being designed for flight, so it must meet rigorous thermal, vacuum, weight, power, volume, vibration, shock, and EMI/EMC requirements. These specifications are still (as of the writing of this paper) being refined, but the basic requirements are as follows.

The AVGS shall have a square field-of-view of 14 to 16 degrees. The AVGS shall be capable of acquiring and tracking an arrangement of short-range targets (spaced at least 66 cm apart) out to a minimum range of 300 meters, returning the range and bearing to the targets. The full 6-DOF information is not available until the short-range targets can be imaged separately. The AVGS shall be able to acquire and track a single short-range target, returning the relative positions and attitudes, from 0.5 meters out to 30 meters. The AVGS shall provide updated measurements, during tracking mode, at a frequency no less than 20 Hz. The

system shall be capable of acquiring a target in less than one second. The sensor must be capable of performing properly under any lighting conditions as long as the sun is not within 15 degrees of the camera's bore sight. The accuracy of the sensor within 30 meters of range is specified in the table below:

Table 1: AVGS Measurement Accuracy Requirements

Operating Range (m)	X-Offset (mm)	Y-Offset Z-Offset (mm)	Roll/Pitch/Yaw (Degrees)
1 – 3	+3	+2	+0.3
> 3 – 5	+10	+5	+0.75
> 5 – 10.5	+100	+50	+1
>10.5 - 30	+300	+100	+2

The AVGS shall be able to track targets that move across the FOV with an apparent angular rate of up to 2.0 degrees per second. The AVGS shall have a physical envelope of no more than 12" X 12" X 12" (30.5 cm X 30.5 cm X 30.5 cm). This is a short summary of the more relevant portions of the requirements for the AVGS.

Schedule

The preliminary design work began in 2000. A small amount of funding was allocated in FY2001 to build a prototype, and the DART experiment was approved in mid FY2001. The brass-board AVGS will be completed in November of 2001. It will be used to ensure the basic functionality of the AVGS and to perform testing to confirm the soundness of the overall design. The flight versions of the AVGS will be completed by mid 2003. They will then undergo full functional and environmental testing.

Applications for the AVGS

The AVGS has applications for automated spacecraft guidance, pilot assistance for spacecraft guidance, automated robotic guidance, assisting robotic guidance, unmanned ground vehicles, non-contact position and attitude monitoring, and measuring robotic end-effector POSE. The AVGS will be useful anywhere that full non-contact 6-

DOF relative position and attitude measurements are desired.

Conclusions

The AVGS will be a very useful sensor for automated spacecraft docking. It will provide useful range and bearing estimates at long ranges and accurate relative 6-degree-of-freedom measurements at closer ranges. The AVGS will be flying on the DART (Demonstration of Autonomous Rendezvous Technology) in about three years.

References

[1] Calhoun, Phil and Richard Dabney, 1995, "A solution to the problem of determining the relative 6 DOF state for spacecraft automated rendezvous and docking", *Proceedings of SPIE Space Guidance, Control, and Tracking II*, Vol. 2466, pp. 175-184.

[2] 1997, "Video Guidance Sensor Flight Experiment Configuration End Item Specification, Part I", MSFC-SPEC-2614 A.

[3] Howard, Richard, Thomas Bryan, and Michael Book, 1999, "On-Orbit Testing of the Video Guidance Sensor", *Proceedings of SPIE Laser Radar Technology and Applications IV*, Vol. 3707, pp. 290-300.

[4] 1997, "SPARTAN/Automated Rendezvous and Capture Video Guidance Sensor Flight Experiment Requirements", MSFC-RQMT-2615 A.

[5] Howard, Richard, Thomas Bryan, and Michael Book, 1998, "Video Guidance Sensor Flight Experiment Results", *Proceedings of SPIE Laser Radar Technology and Applications III*, Vol. 3380, pp. 315-325.

[6] Howard, Richard, Thomas Bryan, Michael Book and Richard Dabney, 1999, "The Video Guidance Sensor – A Flight Proven Technology", *Proceeding of the 22nd Annual American Astronautical Society Guidance and Control Conference*, Vol. 101, pp. 281-298.